

Supplementary Material for Research Paper “*Context, Content, Consent – How to Design User-Centered Privacy Explanations*”

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1 About

This is the supplementary material for the research paper “*Context, Content, Consent – How to Design User-Centered Privacy Explanations*”. Since the space allocated for research papers did not suffice to elaborate on all research results, this document serves to amend this lack. In particular, more details on the Literature Review (LR) – e.g., inclusion/exclusion criteria, complete list of analyzed papers, etc. – and our study design can be found here.

The specific content of this work is structured as follows. In the next section (Sec 2), we provide background information about different types of explanations that are related to our work. Our research design is explained in more detail in Sec. 3. Results of the LR related to validation of privacy explanations requirements and the conceptualization of them can be found in Sec. 4. Sec. 5 will present additional results about the user study such as demographics which we could not include in the paper due to space limitations but which we consider relevant.

2 Background

2.1 Different Types of Explanations

Explanations cannot only be in the form of direct factual text, but can come in different forms and formulations. And not every explanation is a good fit for every type of user [34,126]. In the context of our work, we reviewed different types of explanations from literature on whether or not they might be useful in the context of privacy. Two explanation types that showed a lot of potential were *contrastive* and *example-based* explanations. Concordantly, we decided to include them within our layered design for privacy explanations.

Within our layered design for privacy explanations, the second layer is a contrastive explanation. Vast research in XAI and social sciences has found contrastive explanations to be an effective way of providing understandable explanations [3,91,99,112,119]. In essence, contrastive explanations compare end users’

wrongful expectations to the reality of the situation. Miller [99] argues that complex explanations can put a considerable cognitive burden on their addressee. Offering a point of comparison is supposed to lower this burden. In the context of privacy, we use contrastive explanations to tell end users in which ways their data will **not** be used, independent of if they choose to agree to data processing or not. By providing them with this information, we aim to increase their understanding of what actually happens to their data, and mitigate wrongful worries of possible data misuse.

The third layer of our design for privacy explanations contains example-based explanations. Contemporary explainability literature has identified visual examples as a suitable way to provide understandable explanations to end users [3,27,61]. In the context of privacy, by showing the end user what their data might look like when it is processed, we aim to clarify what is being shared exactly. Fu and Lindqvist [53] argue that a wrongful understanding about how data is being processed can push end users to make decision that do not suit their actual privacy preferences. For instance, they found that end users do not have a precise understanding of what the term “approximate location” entails. Using visual example can remedy this issue, as we can show the user a concrete example of what the requested data would look like. At the same time, we can use the examples provide the explanations’ addressees with additional context.

3 Research Design

In our previous work [24], we conducted a survey on Privacy Explanations. We asked the participants about the benefits and perceptions of privacy explanations. This data is part of our foundation for this current work, in which we have reviewed and validated the survey data through literature and broadened our knowledge in this topic area.

3.1 Literature Review

Our LR is the second pillar for our concepts. We followed guidelines from Kitchenham et al. [79], and Wohlin [140] when conducting our LR. The starting set for our LR originates from a previously conducted SLR in the field of explainability [32]. We extended it by conducting additional steps of snowballing and a data base search in the direction of privacy explanations. Our LR process is depicted in Fig.1.

3.1.1 Process of Literature Analysis

Our starting point (baseline papers, cf. Fig.1) for our LR, was the work of Chazette et al. [32] on the topic of Explainability. We scanned their final set (229 papers) for relevance concerning the non-functional requirements (NFRs) explainability, privacy, transparency trust, trustworthiness, and understandability. From the results of survey we conducted, we identified these as critical quality

Fig. 1. Process of literature analysis

aspects in connection to privacy explanations. After reviewing the baseline papers according to our selection process (Section 3.1.2), we retrieved a start set of 45 papers.

After retrieving the start set, we complemented it with Snowballing. We conducted the snowballing process in accordance with Wohlin [140] in both forward and backward direction. For the purposes of this work, we stopped the snowballing once we reached a “theoretical saturation”, following grounded theory, as introduced by Wolfswinkel et al. [141]. This means that we stopped the snowballing process once no new concepts or ideas arose. The snowballing procedure resulted in 44 additional papers.

To further complement the found literature in the direction of privacy, a database search was planned and conducted. Yasnin et al. [143] researched the suitability of Google Scholar for literature reviews. They state that Google Scholar retrieved 96% of primary studies. on Google Scholar. Therefore, we consider Google Scholar appropriate for performing database searches in the context of a literature search. Referring to Brereton et al. [21], we decided to derive three different search terms from our Paper Set 2 to obtain more precise results. The first search string focused on literature that investigates the relationship between privacy statements, trustworthiness, and usability.

(explainability AND privacy) AND (usability OR trustworthiness OR “privacy explanation” OR “explainable privacy”) AND (-ai -xai -machine -neural-recommender)

The search yielded 83 papers, four of which were deemed relevant. The goal of the second search string was to identify literature that examines the relationships between privacy statements and consent.

allintitle: *(privacy) AND (explanation OR statement OR notice OR consent) AND (-ai -xai -machine -neural -recommender)*

In this search, we identified 173 papers, of which we selected 13 as relevant. In our third search, we focused on privacy in the context of mobile applications, since smart devices occupy a very prominent place in the daily use of digital systems. In this search, we deliberately excluded the topic area around Covid-19 because a large number have arisen since 2019 and we did not want to limit our research here as a result.

allintitle: *(app AND privacy) AND (mobile OR smartphone) AND (-covid)*

The third search enabled us to identify 123 papers, of which we subsequently selected 24 as relevant. Thus, the database search returned a total of 41 papers. With these 41 papers we performed snowballing again, however, this did not lead to any new findings, so we have reached saturation here according to grounded theory [141]. The final set of our LR thus contained 130 papers.

3.1.2 Publication Selection

We included paper that met the following inclusion criteria (IC):

IC_1 Address one or more of our research questions

IC_2 Were published between 01/1984 and 01/2022

IC_3 Are peer-reviewed publications such as journal, conference, and workshop

and we excluded publications that met the following exclusion criteria (EC):

EC_1 Are non English-language publications

EC_2 Are tutorials, proposals, and other non-peer reviewed publications

EC_3 Works from after 2019 should not only be focused on the ongoing Covid-19 pandemic

We followed the starting point of Chazette et al.’s work [32] to avoid excluding concepts that are relevant to our work. To include a publication, all inclusion criteria must be met. If at least one of the exclusion criteria was met, the publication was rejected. Formally expressed:

$$(IC_1 \wedge IC_2 \wedge IC_3) \wedge \neg(EC_1 \vee EC_2 \vee EC_3)$$

We manually reviewed all of the publications by judging their relevance regarding our inclusion & exclusion criteria. We applied a two-phase selection procedure. In phase one, we have selected candidate papers based on title, abstract, and keywords. We have also analyzed the conclusion section in cases where the aforementioned elements did not provide sufficient information. EC_3 did not apply in this phase. In phase two, we have selected papers based on full text and also applied EC_3 . The procedure was the same for manual search and snowballing.

3.1.3 List of Selected Papers

The following papers are the result of our LR process with respect to our selection procedure.

Start set: [1], [2], [3], [7], [6], [17], [26], [32], [27], [33], [35], [42], [55], [56], [61], [66], [69], [80], [81], [76], [86], [87], [89], [90], [97], [99], [104], [108], [110], [111], [113], [116], [119], [122], [131], [132], [133], [134], [135], [139], [140], [141], [146], [147], [148].

Paper Set 2: [5], [14], [20], [29], [31], [36], [38], [39], [40], [41], [44], [45], [46], [47], [48], [51], [52], [58], [60], [62], [63], [65], [68], [70], [72], [75], [78], [83], [88], [94], [101], [107], [112], [114], [117], [118], [121], [125], [126], [127], [136], [138], [144], [145].

Data base search: [4], [8], [9], [10], [11], [13], [15], [18], [25], [28], [30], [37], [43], [49], [57], [59], [64], [67], [73], [74], [77], [82], [84], [85], [92], [93], [95], [96], [98], [100], [102], [103], [105], [106], [115], [123], [124], [130], [137], [142], [149].

3.2 Data Validation Process and Knowledge Extraction

To validate our findings from the survey, first and foremost the requirements for privacy explanations, we inspected the existing privacy literature. Our focus was on details about information that should be made available and accessible to end users as well as what value it has for end users in relation to their privacy needs and attitudes. Privacy regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [50] of the European Union or the California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA) [128] of the United States require service providers to inform end users about their data practices in ways required by law. In addition to this information, we also looked at what the literature says about users' needs and what they should know beyond that to gain control over their privacy and make appropriate decisions.

3.3 User Study

We followed established guidelines for survey design [71,129] in order to ensure the quality of our survey. We conducted two rounds of pilot testing to evaluate the survey's quality. They took place with members of our research group. Based on our insights from these pilot tests, we made some minor corrections such as minor text changes for better understanding.

Our user study had 61 participants and consisted of three main sections. It was provided in the form of an online survey, which included two questionnaires and an interactive section in the middle. The interactive section made use of the software prototype shown in section 4.3. While completing the questionnaires and interacting with the prototype, participants were asked to comment their decision processes and give reasons for their answers. This is referred to as the

“Think-Aloud” approach [16]. Their comments and remarks were later subject to two cycles of coding, in accordance with Saldaña’s [120] method: an initial cycle of *in vivo* coding and a later cycle of pattern coding.

We commenced our three part study with a demographic questionnaire, which included common demographic factors such as gender identity and age, as well as a set of questions concerning the participants’ privacy preconceptions and behavior. When the participants completed the first part of the questionnaire, they were presented with a hypothetical, privacy-related scenario, within which they were asked to navigate the privacy explanation prototype. This scenario can be condensed as follows:

You want to go on a vacation abroad. Before leaving, you have read up on travel guide apps and found something that you want to use. The app in question is supposed to give you travel suggestions based on what is close to you. As you are moving to install the app from the app store, a privacy explanation opens up. Please navigate the prototype at your own discretion.

After participants were done exploring the prototype, the study concluded with a questionnaire about the prototype and the privacy explanations used within it. This included questions about the structure, the contents and the credibility of the privacy explanations, and whether or not the participants found them to be relevant to their privacy needs.

4 Results – Literature Review

After describing our research approach in section 3, here is an overview of the results of our LR, which we were not able to include in our paper “*Context, Content, Consent – How to Design User-Centered Privacy Explanations*” due to space limitations.

4.1 Privacy Explanation Requirements

The following is the data collected regarding privacy explanation requirements. The data came from our LR and, in addition to validating our elicited requirements from [24], also served to expand our knowledge so that we can expand our requirements in terms of additional knowledge gained. We have retained the structure of the requirements in the four clusters (data usage, data storage, confidentiality, and presentation form) as in [24].

4.1.1 Data Usage

Regarding data practices, it is important to inform and educate users about why their data is being collected, how it is being done, what private information is involved [11,23,50,53,105,108,109], and the impact of not consenting to the use of a particular service [15,82,137].

4.1.2 Data Storage

In addition to educating end users about the use of their personal information, it is also important to inform them about data storage. This includes where the data is stored, for how long, whether it is sufficiently protected and whether it can be deleted [12,50,142].

4.1.3 Confidentiality

Confidentiality and trustworthiness of personal data is another important factor. It should be made clear whether the data will be passed on or resold, with whom it will be shared, and whether it will be aggregated [11,12,19,103,105,109]. Control over one’s own data leads to trust on the part of users [27,68,116] and in turn strengthens trust in the service provider.

4.1.4 Presentation Form

A major problem with privacy policies is that they are too long, incomprehensible and vaguely formulated, and not or insufficiently structured. For privacy explanations, it is therefore important that they are well structured and formulated in a short and concise manner. The tone should not be technical and simple language should be used. [3,18,22,32,43,95,105,109,137]

4.2 The Concept of our Layered Approach

Different users have different needs when it comes to explanations [56,122,126]. To address this need, numerous research efforts have proposed the idea of personalized [56,75,122,126,133] or layered explanations [43,110,121]. In order to accommodate as many users with different privacy attitudes as possible without having to store their preferences in a system in advance and thus to keep the effort for the users as low as possible, we have adapted the concept of layered explanations for our privacy explanations.

Figure 2 show the layered concept. To meet our privacy explanations requirements, end users must be fully educated about data practices. At the same time, it is important not to overburden the user and thereby endanger the usability of a system. The layered concept addresses these challenges by informing the user about data practices in more and more detail, layer by layer, while respecting the different privacy attitudes of the users. Each user can decide for himself how detailed he wants to be informed about his privacy.

4.3 Conceptualization & Prototyping

To test and evaluate our concept of layered privacy explanations, we implemented our design within a high-fidelity prototype. We chose five exemplary data types, for which we displayed the five explanation layers each. Screenshots of the prototype can be seen in Figures 3 and 4. The structure of the explanation layers within the prototype is visualized in Figure 5.

Fig. 2. Layered concept of privacy explanations

Fig. 3. Contrastive Explanation in Prototype

Fig. 4. Example-based Explanation in Prototype

Fig. 5. Structure of Explanation Layers in Prototype

5 Results – User Study

5.1 Demography

The recruitment of our user study participants was done through our academic and personal networks. From among the 61 participants, 38% identified as female and 62% identified as male; none identified as non-binary gender. All participants were at least 18 years old and had completed high school. 57% of them had academic degrees (Bachelor’s degree or higher). 90% of participants were digital natives, meaning they were born after 1980 [35]. With 89%, the vast majority of participants used software within their daily work-life. 72% said that they spend at least 3 hours of their daily free time on the Internet. Furthermore, 87% stated that they regularly use social networks. From these factors, we can reasonably assume that the majority of participants was well-educated and technologically literate.

5.2 Privacy Preconceptions

Before interacting with the prototype, participants answered questions concerning their own privacy preconceptions and behavior. The majority of participants found that the protection of their personal data is important to them. Moreover, they were able to differentiate between different types of personal data. On the one hand, medical data, bank data and personal photos were seen as particularly vulnerable. On the other hand, some data types were considered to be less sensible, such as participants’ interests, search history or location data. All participants were aware of third party data processing. This implies sensitivity on behalf of the participants, in the context of their online privacy.

Despite their educational and technological background, participants showed a lack of care when it came to their actual privacy behavior. Underlining the findings of Brunotte et al. [22], the majority of participants in our study stated that they do not regularly read privacy policies. 54% even said that they never read them at all. 47% of participants did not know what rights the GDPR [50] provides them with, even though all of them were EU citizens. This discrepancy between end-users’ privacy intentions and their actual privacy behavior reinforces the notion of the privacy paradox [54].

5.3 Further Results concerning the Prototype

While the main paper’s results focus on explanation relevancy and understandability, we also questioned participants concerning their general liking of the privacy explanations’ structure and content. Furthermore, we asked them whether or not they found the presented explanations to be credible. Figure 6 shows the results of these lines of questioning. Notably, among the participants who expressed liking for the explanations, not all found them to be credible.

Fig. 6. General Liking and Credibility of Privacy Explanation

After navigating the prototype, participants were also asked to evaluate the explanation scope for every layer. We wanted to find out if our explanations were perceived as being too long or too short, or if participants thought that the scope was just right. The results of this inquiry are seen in Figure 7. Notably, there is a trend of the third party explanation being perceived as too short.

Fig. 7. Perceived Scope of Explanation Layers in Prototype

5.4 Think Aloud Comments

Throughout their participation in the study, participants were asked to voice their thoughts and reasonings aloud. This accounts for both the questionnaire as well as the prototype sessions. Note that the following tables contain only the results of the second coding cycle, which was the pattern coding. To provide a better overview, we subdivided the pattern codes into categories, namely desired *Privacy Explanation Structure* and *Privacy Explanation Contents* as well as participants *Privacy Explanation Preferences* and their *Privacy Awareness*. The tables show the codes, the number of participants associated with each code and their IDs.

Table 1. Privacy Explanation Structure

Code	Count	Participants
Keep PEs short	16	1, 8, 11, 19, 30, 36, 38, 41, 46, 47, 49, 52, 53, 54, 55, 59
Keep PEs long enough	4	3, 8, 41, 52
Offer intuitive consent management	19	1, 4, 7, 9, 12, 14, 19, 23, 25, 29, 31, 33, 35, 38, 44, 47, 48, 53, 58
Offer intuitive navigation	20	4, 9, 12, 16, 17, 20, 24, 28, 29, 33, 36, 39, 44, 45, 49, 51, 53, 55, 59, 60
Provide useful links	14	1, 3, 18, 20, 28, 34, 35, 42, 45, 47, 50, 52, 56, 57
Use professional optics	7	2, 14, 15, 18, 31, 42, 55
Offer operability	25	2, 4, 7, 9, 11, 12, 13, 14, 16, 29, 30, 31, 33, 38, 41, 43, 46, 47, 50, 51, 56, 57, 59, 60, 61
Offer precise operability	10	2, 4, 5, 9, 19, 30, 36, 43, 44, 53
Break up PE structure	24	1, 13, 15, 18, 19, 21, 26, 29, 30, 31, 33, 34, 38, 39, 41, 47, 48, 50, 52, 53, 54, 55, 56, 58
Avoid repetition	11	6, 8, 31, 43, 44, 47, 48, 50, 55, 57, 60
Offer prominent bundled decline	16	3, 4, 12, 25, 30, 31, 34, 35, 36, 42, 43, 48, 50, 56, 58, 61
Avoid false hierarchies	9	15, 24, 27, 30, 36, 45, 53, 57, 61

Table 2. Privacy Explanation Contents

Code	Count	Participants
Avoid unclear wording	29	1, 3, 6, 9, 10, 12, 13, 14, 18, 19, 21, 23, 25, 26, 29, 30, 31, 35, 36, 37, 41, 43, 44, 47, 48, 50, 58, 60, 61
Avoid misunderstandings	14	8, 9, 11, 12, 24, 26, 27, 28, 31, 38, 43, 56, 57, 60
Avoid language barriers	2	8, 21
Build trust	8	9, 16, 17, 22, 42, 45, 46, 52
Consider context	2	9, 52
Offer understandability	24	1, 10, 13, 14, 15, 16, 21, 22, 26, 27, 29, 30, 31, 33, 40, 43, 50, 51, 54, 56, 58, 59, 60, 61
Offer transparency	5	1, 19, 23, 27, 43
Be honest about negatives	23	1, 7, 19, 20, 23, 27, 30, 36, 37, 39, 43, 44, 45, 47, 48, 49, 50, 52, 55, 56, 57, 58, 60
Offer Verifiability	8	23, 36, 39, 45, 52, 53, 54, 59

Table 3. Privacy Explanation Preferences

Code	Count	Participants
Tell "What if not"	6	8, 35, 50, 55, 57, 59
Address users' worries	18	2, 13, 16, 22, 26, 27, 29, 31, 35, 45, 48, 49, 50, 52, 54, 56, 59, 61
Provide helpful examples	26	2, 4, 9, 12, 14, 21, 25, 27, 28, 29, 30, 33, 34, 36, 39, 40, 44, 45, 47, 49, 50, 51, 54, 57, 60, 61
Do not nec. provide contrast	11	10, 11, 15, 17, 20, 21, 34, 41, 43, 51, 55
Do not nec. provide examples	9	1, 3, 8, 17, 19, 20, 31, 35, 46
Do not nec. provide details	3	17, 19, 21
Provide PE as whole	15	14, 16, 19, 22, 27, 28, 30, 37, 46, 49, 50, 52, 53, 58, 59

Note: nec. → necessarily

Table 4. Privacy Awareness

Code (Pre-Prototype)	Count	Participants
Believe that they do not do enough	3	3, 4, 40
Accept privacy trade-offs	23	5, 11, 16, 17, 19, 20, 24, 25, 28, 31, 33, 34, 38, 46, 47, 50, 52, 53, 54, 55, 56, 57, 60
Have "nothing to hide"	10	6, 9, 10, 15, 27, 28, 31, 33, 45, 60
Experience privacy apathy	12	9, 18, 19, 27, 29, 42, 47, 48, 50, 55, 59, 61
Feel forced into sharing data	9	9, 14, 19, 33, 43, 45, 47, 50, 59
Trust state institutions	13	12, 14, 16, 17, 19, 20, 21, 30, 38, 44, 50, 52, 53
See intentional confusion	7	1, 11, 13, 19, 27, 28, 57
Fear criminal activity	5	2, 4, 22, 26, 59
Data scandals raised PA	3	1, 21, 24
Code (Post-Prototype)	Count	Participants
Would not read entire PE	12	1, 6, 8, 15, 20, 23, 25, 39, 43, 54, 55, 60
Think PEs are not trustworthy	7	7, 11, 17, 20, 29, 40, 48,
Feel PE increased PA	9	7, 15, 20, 27, 34, 43, 50, 53, 56
Feel PA effects are only short-term	5	4, 39, 53, 54, 57
Have high PA not increased further	8	1, 23, 31, 42, 43, 45, 46, 48

Note: Gauging privacy awareness increase requires comparing participants sentiments before and after interaction with the prototype.

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